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Biological control and pathogenicity of the *Fusarium oxysporum* caused onion wilt in different localities of sindh and baltistan region

Mhammad Ayub¹, Shahid Hussain^{2*}, Muhammad Rasheed³, Rahila Rahim⁴, Mehreen Hussain⁵, Shabbir Hassan⁶

¹⁻⁵ Pakistan agricultural research council (PARC) MARS Skardu, Pakistan

⁶ Tusi Scientific Research Center Kowardu, Pakistan

Abstract

In arrange to verify the pathogenic character of isolated fungus *F. oxysporum* the (*f.sp Cepa*) the pathogenicity test was conducted on commonly growing onion variety Hazari by root and shoot infestation method. In general these methods of inoculation showed substantial impact on disease development and plant growth. Onion germination was significantly reduced in pots either inoculated by shoot or root infestation method as compared to the un-inoculated plants (control). However, root infestation method caused maximum reduction in plant germination (60%) followed by shoot infestation method (39% as compared to control). Similar trend were also observed in plant mortality, where highest plant mortality were recorded in root infestation method as compared to control (28%). Significant differences were also observed between plant growth in inoculated and un- inoculated plants. The plant growth parameters were also significantly varied with method of inoculation. Minimum root length were recorded in shoot infestation method (5.34 cm) as compared to control (10.74 cm). Similarly minimum root weight were recorded in root infestation method (1776 mg) followed by shoot infestation method (1296 mg) as compared to control (0,22 mg). Reisolation of the inoculated fungus was confirmed as of pathogenic nature *F. oxysporum* was re-isolated significantly in higher frequency in root infestation method (84.78%) as compared to shoot infestation method also showed some infection of *F. oxysporum* (10%). It could be either due to the soil-borne nature of the *F oxysporum* or as a result of secondary infection from inoculated plants. During the studies regarding the management it was found that the disease can be managed significantly through certain management strategies like by the use of *Trichoderma verdii*.

Keywords: re-isolated, biological control, root and shoot infestation, pathogenicity

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is herbaceous crop found all over the world. At world Laval onion production has improved by at least 25 to 30% over the past 10 years with recent production being around 45 million tonnes make it the second most essential crop after tomatoes (Griffiths *et al.*, 2002) [21].

According to an estimate, the area under onion and potato crops during 2013- 14 was 127.8 and 169.9 thousand hectares, respectively, whereas production of onion and potato crops was 1,661.3 and 3,507.1 thousand tonnes, respectively. It is estimated that the total world production of onion was about 86.34 mt and Pakistan occupied 8th position with 2.25% share in production (Anum *et al.*, 2015) [6].

The Fusarium wilt disease is incited by *Fusarium oxysporium* and is a disease complex problem which is caused by the activity of more than one fungus like *F. oxysporium*, *F. solani*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Pythium* and *Macrophomina phaseolina* spp (Dar *et al.*, 2011) [13].

Onion is attacked by many diseases ilke Purple blotch (*Alternaria porri*) Black mold (*Aspergillus Niger*) Neck rot (*Botrytis aclada*) Smudge (*Colletotrichum circinans*) Fusarium wilt *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *Cepa* (Grooten, 2012) [22].

The biological control action of these species is chiefly attributable to a mixture of several mechanisms of action,

which may affect the micropholora of the suppressiveness of compost the addition species of *Trichoderma* to dung is a common technique used to control different plant diseases to suppress Fusarium wilt evaluated by species of *Trichoderma* (Blaya *et al.*, 2013).

The antagonistic activity of two species of *Trichoderma*, *T. harzianum* and *T. viride* were tested on PDA against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp.*cepa* by dual culture inoculation technique among the bioagent, *Trichoderma viride* inhibited maximum growth as compare to *Trichoderma harzianum* (Ilhe *et al.*, 2013) [2].

Therefore keeping in view the losses caused by the Fusarium wilt of onion, the aim of the study is to find out the most effective and eco-friendly approach to minimize the losses and manage the wilt disease in field of onion.

Materials and Methods

Survey of infected fields

A survey of onion fields of districts Hyderabad, Mirpurkhas, Tandoallahyar, Khrmang, Khpulo and Shigar from baltian region was carried out to record the occurrence of Fusarium wilt.

Disease severity

During the survey observations were recorded on the

incidence of the Fusarium wilt of onion fields. The Disease in severity of the disease was calculated according to the disease incidence formula.

$$\text{Disease severity (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of wilted plants}}{\text{Total No. of plants}} \times 100$$

Isolation and identification of the disease causing fungus

Samples were taken from infected shoots, bulbs, and roots of infect onions. Collected samples were then bring to the laboratory for isolation and identification process as described by Pathak, (1987) [38], where, the samples were first surface sterilized twice with distilled sterilized water and then were treated with 0.5% NaOCl (Sodium hypochlorite) for 2 minutes. After surface sterilization the samples were dried on sterilized blotter papers and placed in petriplates containing sterilized potato dextrose agar medium. All the petridishes were incubated at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for about seven days. After seven days of inoculation the fungi isolated, were then identified with the help of keys for identification of fungi by Nelson *et al.*, (1983) [37] and with the help of characteristics of fungi mentioned in the book “The Isolation and Identification of Fungi” by Frank. M. Dugan (2005) [18].

Identification of *Fusarium* spp

Fusarium spp. isolated from infected tissues of roots and shoots were then identified by studying their colony characteristics and conidial morphology using the keys described by Nelson *et al.* (1983) [37] and with the help of characteristics of fungi mentioned in the book “The Isolation and Identification of Fungi” by Frank. M. Dugan.

General characteristics of *Fusarium oxysporum*

Mycelium appeared just like yellow, reddish-brown or blue-black in color. Macroconidia short, straight, or 40-75 x 25.5-5 micron and long 5-8 septate. Microconidia consist of 1-3 septate, with a short beak and 22-48 x 3.4 microns (Salam *et al.*, 2015).

Biological control

This study was conducted to assess the efficacy bio-control agent *Trichoderma verdii* against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *Cepa*, by using dual culture method as described by Bahareh *et al.* (2016) [8]. The five millimeter diameter mycelial colony disc of test antagonist *Trichoderma verdii* was taken from seven days old culture this was paired against same sized mycelial disc of *Fusarium oxysporum* at opposed ends of petri plates. The petri plates were incubated at the $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature for eight days to observe the colony grow inhibition percentage of the pathogen was calculated as explained by Anupama (2015) [7]. The inhibition growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* in the presence of *Trichoderma verdii* was calculated over control. The growth inhibition was calculated by following formula:

$$(\text{R1}-\text{R2}) \times 100$$

Where,

R1= Radial mycelial colony dual pathogen in control.

R2= Radial mycelial colony growth of pathogen in dual culture experiment with antagonists.

Pathogenicity Test of the Fungus

The Pathogenicity Test of most predominant fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* was done by mixing of the fresh inoculums of the fungus with 1kg of sterilized soil in pots. Thirty onion plants sown in pots containing infested and un-infested soil. The data was recorded on number of healthy and infected plants and disease incidence severity and disease mortality after 35 days. The experiment was conducted in completely randomized block design (RCBD), with 3 treatments and 3 replications.

Conidial suspension

For injection, conidial solution was ready from 2 weeks old culture of *Fusarium oxysporum*. Clean water was added in each culture plate of the test fungus order to harvest fungus conidia; the culture was gently rubbed with spatula. The spore solution was collect in an uncontaminated glass beaker and strained through muslin cloth. Conidial concentration (conidia/ml) were determined with the help of hemocytometer and adjusted by adding water.

Root Infestation Method

An onion root was dipped in 100 ml of spore suspension for five minutes. The un-infested onion plants were used as control. Five seedlings of both infested and un-infested control plants were grown per pot (containing 2 kg /per pot). Four replications of every inoculated and un-inoculated were carry out. These pots were kept in un-wrap air and watered as per requirement. After 35 days of sowing, the plants were uprooted carefully. The data were recorded plant mortality, plant growth and root infection.

Shoot Infestation Method

The already prepared fungal suspension iject in shoots of onion two kg soil was filled in each earthen pot. Three plants were sown in each infested and un-infested (control pots). The experiment was arranged as Randomized complete Block Design with three replications. These pots were kept in open air and watered as prequirement. Later than 45 days of sow, the plants were uprooted cautiously. The statistics were recorded on, i, e mortality and plant growth.

Re-isolation of the inoculated fungus

Re-isolation was made from inoculated and uninoculated plants. For this principle, the roots and shoots of the plant was washed carefully with tap water and cut into small pieces after surface sterilization with alchohal solution, pieces were placed on PDA plates. The recovery of inoculated fungus was recorded and disease percent was calculated with the help of following formula:

$$\text{Infection \%} = \frac{\text{NO. Of spp colonized by the fungus}}{\text{Tot no. of sp. studied}} \times 100$$

Results

1. Survey of different onion fields

A Survey of different onion fields of district Hyderabad, Tandolayar and Mirpurkhas, Kharmang Shigar and Khapulo was carried out to observe the incidence of Fusarium wilt in the onion fields of these districts. During the survey it was

observed that almost all the onion fields were suffering from some severe diseases like, Purple blotch *Alternaria porri*, *Aspergillus niger*, Neck rot (*Botrytis aclada*) Smudge (*Colletotrichum circinans*) Fusarium wilt *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *Cepa*. Blue mold (*Penicillium spp*) Downy mildew (*Peronospora destructor*) Onion smut (*Urocystis cepulae*) (Grooten, 2012) [22]. Fusarium basal rot (*Fusarium oxysporum*). Among all of them, the Fusarium wilt was found most dominating disease throughout all the onion fields visited. The maximum disease incidence was recorded from Hyderabad (60.0%) whereas, the disease incidence in district Mirpurkhas was bit low as compared to district Tando Layar, maximum incidence of Fusarium wilt recorded from district Hyderabad was (60.0%) (Table.1).

2. Isolation and identification of the fungus causing Fusarium wilt of onion

The collected infected specimens were then brought to laboratory for isolation and identification process of the fungus caused. The isolation and identification process reveals the association of different kinds of the pathogens with the

wilted parts of the Onion shoots. Among all the isolated fungi, *Fusarium oxysporum* remains most frequent and pre-dominant fungus and was recognized on the bases of their siz and shaps mentioned in the book “identification of the fungi” written by Frank M. Dugan (2005) [18] and with the help of electronic microscope, help from the senior Professors of the department was also taken in this regard.

Evaluvation of *Trichoderma verdii* against *Fusarium oxysporum* in vitro conditions.

Trichoderma verdii was tested *in-vitro* conditions against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *Cepa*, for this purpose dual-culture method was used and both the fungus the *Trichoderma verdii* and *Fusarium oxysporum* were placed in same plates at opposed from each other *Trichoderma verdii* extensively reduced the mycelia colony growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* at (P< 0.05) In the dual- culture the growth of *Trichoderma verdii* was proved (48mm) and *Fusarium oxysporum* (23mm) compared to control *Trichoderma verdii* (84 mm) and control *Fusarium oxysporum* (86mm).

Table 1: Disease incidence of Fusarium wilt of Onion fields in three districts of Sindh during servay.

Locality	No. Of Fields visited	Samples taken/per Fields	Samples studied			
			Diseased	Healthy	Total	Severity %
Mirpurkhas	04	25	45	55	100	45.00
Hyderabad	04	25	60	40	100	60.00
Tando Layar	04	25	48	52	100	48.00
Kharmang	04	25	30	40	100	30.00
Shigar	04	25	30	70	100	30.00
Khapulo	04	25	40	45	100	40.00

Graph 1: Highest Disease incidence of Fusarium wilted fields in three districts during servay.

Pathogenicity of fusarium wilt

In arrange to verify the pathogenic character of isolated fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* the f.sp, *cepa*) the pathogenicity test was conducted on commonly growing onion variety Hazari by root and shoot infestation method. In general these methods of inoculation showed substantial impact on disease development and plant growth.

Onion germination was significantly reduced in pots either inoculated by shoot or root infestation method as compared to the un-inoculated plants (control). However, root infestation method caused maximum reduction in plant germmation (60%) followed by shoot infestation method (39% as comparod to control) (Fig 1). Similar trend were also observed in plant mortality, where highest plant mortality were recorded in root infestation method as compared to control (28%).

Significant differences were also observed between plant growth in inoculated and un- inoculated plants. The plant growth parameters were also significantly varied with method of inoculation. Minimum root length were recorded in shoot infestation method (5.34 cm) as compared to control (10.74 cm) (Fig. 2),

Similarly minimum root weight were recordod in root infestation method (1776 mg) followed by shoot infestation method (1296 mg) as compared to control (0,22 mg) (Fig 4). Reisolation of the inoculated fungus was confirmed as of pathogenic nature *F. oxysporum* was re-isolated significantly in higher frequency in root infestation method (84.78%) as compared to shoot infestation method also showed some infection of *F. oxysporum* (10%). It could be either due to the soil-bome nature of the *F oxysporum* or as a result of secondary infection from inoculated plants.

Graph 4: Showing Disease mortality of onions

Graph 5: showing root length of onions

Effect of *Fusarium oxysporum* on (1) disease mortality and (2) Root length of onion plant

Graph 6: Showing Disease infection of onions

Graph 7: Showing root weight of onions

Effect of *Fusarium oxysporum* on (1) disease Infection % and (2) Root weight of onion plant

Fig 1: Photograph showing the survey of different infected onion fields of Fusarium wilt.

(A) District Hyderabad (Tandojam) Tando alyar District Mirpurkhas

Fig 2: the pure culture the fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* after 8 days of inoculation

Discussion

Fusarium wilt is most serious and devastating disease of onion field throughout the world including Pakistan especially in Sindh province district Hyderabad, which causes serious losses to young plants and may lead to their death. So, therefore keeping in view the incidence and the losses caused by the disease in onion field, the survey of three, districts of Sindh, e.g. Hyderabad, Tandolayar and Mirpurkhas was carried out to record the incidence of the disease in different onion fields of these three districts. During the survey it was observed that the Fusarium wilt of onion was found frequently in all the onion fields of the three districts with more or less incidence. The maximum incidence was recorded from Hyderabad district (60.0%) whereas, the incidence of the disease from the Mirpurkhas district was recorded up to (45.0%). These studies were investigated by Wrather and Phipps, (2002) [53] and Montgomery, (2009) [36], who found 50-70% and 9.4 % infection on cotton due to *Fusarium spp.* Moreover Khanzada *et al.*, (2004) [10] reported 60% mango decline intensity due to soil borne microflora accompanied with *Fusarium oxysporum* also.

The pathogenicity and chemical control of fungal agents of wilt disease in onion were investigated fungal agents of wilt disease, *F. oxysporum*. 42.91% and 53.55 %, *Botrytis allii* Munn 23.88% and 10.07 % *Fusarium acuminatum* (Ellis) Everh. 16.05 % and 10.82 % were determined both in onion roots and bulbs respectively (Ozer, 1995).

In our studies, isolation and identification of the collected diseased specimens showed the association of three fungi i-e., *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Aspergillus Niger*, *Botrytis* from rotted roots and shoot tissues. Among them *Fusarium oxysporum* was found in highest frequency from all the associated fungi. The isolated fungi were then identified on the basis of morphological characteristics and color of the colonies of fungi. The identification was also done with help of taxonomical keys described by Nelson *et al.*, (1983) [37] and with help of a hand book "isolation and identification of fungi" written by Frank. M. Dugan (2005) [18]. These results are in link with the studies of Grooten (2012) [22] isolated 3 different species of fungal microbes from roots and shoots of diseased onion plant and found that the *Fusarium oxysporum* were frequently associated with fields of onion.

Keeping in view onions has a great economic importance, its export value losses caused by the Fusarium wilt, different management practices like botanical, and biological were carried out under *in-vitro* conditions against the *Fusarium oxysporum* to find out the most effective eco-friendly cost effective and easily available control measure to manage the Fusarium wilt disease of onion Behrani (2015) [10].

Bio-control agent was tested *in-vitro* conditions against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *Cepa*, In the dual- culture the growth of *Trichoderma verdii* was proved (48mm) and *Fusarium oxysporum* (23mm) compared to control *Trichoderma verdii* (84 mm) and control *Fusarium oxysporum* (86mm).

The biocontrol agents *Trichoderma sp* were positive as substitute to chemical control of the onion basal rot and to better growth and yield of onion and inhibited the colony growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* (Malathi, 2015) [34].

Conclusions

The present studies were conducted to report the disease incidence pathogenicity and biological control of *Fusarium* wilt disease of onion fields in three districts of Sindh namely Hyderabad Tandoalyar and Mirpurkhas to find out the more effective measures to manage the onion wilt disease. Our studies showed that *Fusarium* wilt disease of onion is one of the major serious threats to onion fields in Sindh region as compare to GB. During the studies regarding the management it was found that the disease can be managed significantly through certain management strategies like by the use of *Trichoderma verdii*.

Suggestions and Recommendation

Keeping in view the results of present research work, it is suggested *Trichoderma verdii* should be recommended against this disease. Fungicides are hazardous for human health and there is problem of resistance against fungicides, so alternative control is needed, for this purpose *Trichoderma verdii* could be used. These studies also showed that the disease can also be control through botanical extracts and Biological control like *Trichoderma verdii*.

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